

Synthesis of Thiohydantoins, Thiazolidones and Their Derivatives from N¹-(4'-Aryl Thiazole 2'-yl) Thioureas

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Some new heterocyclic substituted thiohydantoins(III) and thiazolidones (VI) have been synthesised from N¹-(4'-aryl thiazole 2'-yl) thioureas(II) with monochloro acetic acid in the medium of pyridine and alcohol with anhydrous sodium acetate respectively. Both the keto-methylene compounds (thiohydantoin and thiazolidone) have been used to prepare several arylidene derivatives and dibromo compounds. The thioureas have also been used to prepare 5,5-diphenyl 3-(4'-aryl thiazole 2'-yl) thiohydantoins (IX) with benzil. These mixed thiohydantoins have been coupled with diazotised sulphanilamide to get the diazo compounds (X).

SYNTHESIS of thioureas from heterocyclic amines by heating them with ammonium thiocyanate in hydrochloric acid medium failed. In our present investigation, we have synthesised four different N¹-(4'-aryl thiazole 2'-yl) thioureas (II) from 2-amino 4-aryl thiazoles with benzoyl thiocyanate and subsequent hydrolysis of the product with alkali. The thioureas, when condensed with monochloro acetic acid in pyridine gave the thiohydantoins (III). Besides the normal function as solvent pyridine acts as a base, abstracting proton from the amidic nitrogen, according to the following reaction scheme.

On the otherhand when the reaction was performed in the medium of alcohol with sodium acetate the thiol form of thiourea gave thiazolidones (VI). The structures of thiohydantoin (III, Ar = C₆H₅) and thiazolidone (VI, Ar = C₆H₅) have been confirmed from I.R. In case of latter, two bands at 1490 cm⁻¹ and 1650 cm⁻¹ indicate C-N and C = N stretching vibrations, but in case of the former these bands are absent.

- 1—C₆H₅COCl, NH₄CNS, NaOH
- 2—ClCH₂COOH, Pyridine
- 3—RCHO, ACOH, NaOAC
- 4—Br₂, ACOH
- 5—C₆H₅OH, NaOAC
- 6—Benzil, NaOEt, EtOH
- 7—pNH₂ C₆H₄ SO₂NH₂, NaNO₂, HCl.

Both the ketomethylene compounds (III and VI) on reacting with aldehydes in acetic acid and anhydrous sodium acetate furnished the arylidene compounds (IV and VII, Tables 4 & 5). The structures of ketomethylene compounds and their arylidene derivatives have been confirmed from I. R. the parent thiohydantoin and thiazolidone have the carbonyl absorption at 1770 cm⁻¹ and 1725 cm⁻¹ respectively but in case of the arylidene derivatives bathochromic shift occurred for the same due to conjugation with the unsaturation at 5-position (bands at 1740 cm⁻¹ and 1675 cm⁻¹). There is also the absence of any peak in the region 2500-2700 cm⁻¹ indicating the absence of carboxyl group in thiohydantoin.

Since the introduction of bromine into the thiazoles, thiazolidones¹⁻³ etc. augments the antifungal and antibacterial activities it was considered worthwhile to prepare the dibromo derivatives (V and VIII) of the arylidene compounds with bromine in acetic acid.

The thiazoyl thioureas (II) were allowed to react with benzil in the presence of sodium ethoxide to 5,5-diphenyl 3-(4'-aryl thiazole 2'-yl) thiohydantoins (IX) according to the following reaction scheme⁴.

5,5-Diphenyl 3-(4'-phenyl thiazole 2'-yl) thiohydantoin structure has been confirmed from I.R. as it gave an absorption at 1730 cm⁻¹ indicating the presence of a carbonyl group. The position 5- of the

thiazole ring in the thiohydantoin (IX) is active⁵⁻⁶. Hence it undergoes coupling with diazotised sulfanilamide to the diazo compound (X)

Bactericidal test: A few of the arylidene derivatives and their dibromo compounds were screened and tested, *in vivo*, against *H.Nana* and *N.Brasi-tiensis* with a dose of 250 mg/kg. None of the compounds were found to be active.

Experimental

All melting points are uncorrected. Infra-red spectra were taken on KBr discs.

2-Amino 4-aryl thiazoles were prepared by heating thiourea (0.1 M), iodine (0.05 M) and the appropriate ketone (0.2 M) following the method of Dodson and King⁷.

N'-(4-phenyl thiazole 2-yl) thiourea :

A solution of ammonium thiocyanate (7.6 gm) in dry acetone (50 ml) was taken in a three necked

flask provided with a reflux condenser, a mechanical stirrer and a dropping funnel, benzoyl chloride (6 ml) was added slowly with stirring. After the addition was complete the mixture was refluxed for half an hour. Then a solution of 2-amino-4-phenyl thiazole (17 g) in dry acetone (25 ml) was added with stirring at such a rate that the solution refluxed gently. The mixture was poured carefully into cold water (1 litre) and the resulting deep yellow precipitate of (*N'*-benzoyl-*N*²-4-phenylthiazole-2-yl-) thiourea was removed by filtration. The crystals were added to a 10% NaOH solution, which was boiled for 15 min. and then cooled. After removing a small amount of insoluble material by filtration the solution was acidified with conc. HCl and made alkaline with NH₄OH. On cooling, the solution deposited a pale yellow crystalline product. It was filtered, dried, and crystallised from alcohol acetone (2 : 1) mixture; yield 85%, m.p. 215° (Found S; 27.42. C₁₀H₉N₃S₂ requires S : 27.23%); 3300 cm⁻¹ due to primary amide, 1200 cm⁻¹ due to C = S attached to N.

The analytical data, m.p. etc. of the other thioureas prepared by the above procedure are given in Table 1.

TABLE 1—(THIOUREAS II)

Nature of Ar	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	60	190	24.21	23.74
<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl	65	147	24.06	24.15
<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	50	87	25.67	25.71

3-(4'-phenyl thiazole 2'-yl) thiohydantoin (III, Ar = C₆H₅):

A mixture of N'-(4-phenyl thiazole 2-yl) thiourea (5 g) and monochloro acetic acid (2.6 g) was taken in anhydrous pyridine (10 ml) and the mixture was warmed on a water bath. After 5 min, an exothermic reaction set in. On completion of the reaction it was cooled when a viscous material was obtained. Absolute alcohol (50 ml) was added to it and the mixture was refluxed in an anhydrous condition for 1 to 2 hr. A crystalline substance was obtained, which was recrystallised from methanol. Yield—40%, m.p. 250°; (Found Sulphur; 22.82, C₁₂H₉N₃S₂O requires S; 23.27%) 1420 cm⁻¹ CH deformation in CH₂; 1770 cm⁻¹ C=O; 2900 cm⁻¹ C-H stretching in CH₂; 3200 cm⁻¹ (NH, broad).

The m.p. etc. of the different thiohydantoin prepared by the above procedure are given in Table 2.

TABLE 2—(THIOHYDANTOINS III)

Nature of Ar	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	50	262	21.09	20.67
<i>p</i> -Methoxy phenyl	50	142	21.26	20.98
<i>p</i> -Methyl phenyl	50	168	21.86	22.14

2'-(4'-phenyl thiazole 2'-ylimino) 4-thiazolidone: (VI; Ar = C₆H₅)

A mixture of N'-(4-phenyl thiazole-2-yl) thiourea (5 g), monochloro acetic acid (2.6 g), anhydrous sodium acetate (2 g) in absolute alcohol (50 ml) was heated under reflux for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was distilled to recover excess of ethanol and poured into water when a precipitate was obtained. It was washed several times with hot water to remove unreacted monochloro acetic acid and sodium acetate. Finally the product was crystallised from ethanol. Yield—55%, m.p., 215° (Found Sulphur; 23.56, C₁₂H₉N₃S₂O requires S; 23.27%), 1400 cm⁻¹ CH deformation, 1490 cm⁻¹ C-N stretching, 1650 cm⁻¹ C=N, 1725 cm⁻¹ C=O, 3150 cm⁻¹ (NH, broad).

The analysis and m.p. etc. of the other substituted thiazolidones prepared by the above procedure have been given in Table 3.

2-(4'-Phenyl thiazole-2'-ylimino)5-(benzal)-4-thiazolidone

The above thiazolidone (0.28 g), benzaldehyde (0.2 g) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) in

glacial acetic acid (10 ml) were refluxed over an asbestos centered wire gauze for 2 hr. The clear solution on cooling was poured into water, when a yellow coloured solid separated. It was filtered, dried and crystallised from acetic acid. Yield—65%, m.p. 250°. (Found Sulphur, 16.95, C₁₉H₁₃N₃S₂O requires S; 17.63%) 1520 cm⁻¹ C-N stretching, 1585 cm⁻¹ C=N and C=C, 1675 cm⁻¹ C=O and 3400 cm⁻¹ (NH, broad).

TABLE 3—(THIAZOLIDONES VI)

Nature of Ar	Yield %	M.P. °C	% of Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	50	189	20.35	20.98
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	60	256	20.86	20.67

2-(4'-Phenyl thiazole 2'-ylimino) 5-bromo 5-(α-bromo)-benzyl 4-thiazolidone

A solution of the above benzal derivative (0.01 M) in acetic acid (10 ml) was treated with bromine (0.01 M) in acetic acid (10 ml) in cold. The mixture was kept overnight and the yellow coloured solid separated was washed with ether and finally dried.

The analysis, m.p. etc. of the different arylidene derivatives (VII) and their dibromides (VIII) have been recorded in Table 4.

3-(4'-Phenyl thiazole 2'-yl) 4-(benzal) thiohydantoin

The above thiohydantoin (0.28 g) and benzaldehyde (0.2 g) were refluxed in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) and anhydrous sodium acetate (0.5 g) for 2 hr. The product was isolated as described in the isolation of arylidene thiazolidones. Yield—65%, m.p. 230°; (Found: S, 17.20; C₁₉H₁₃N₃S₂O requires S; 17.63%, 1620 cm⁻¹ C=C; 1740 cm⁻¹, C=O; 3500 cm⁻¹ (NH, broad).

The dibromo compounds were prepared by the method described earlier. The different derivatives prepared from thiohydantoin are recorded in Table 5.

5,5-Diphenyl 3-(4'-phenyl thiazole 2'-yl)thiohydantoin:

Metallic sodium (0.5 g) was dissolved in absolute alcohol (60 ml). N'-(4-phenyl thiazole 2-yl) thiourea (0.3 g) and benzil (1.2 g) were added to this solution and the mixture was refluxed for 1 hr on a water bath. About half of alcohol was distilled off. To the residual solution sodium acetate (5–6 g) with water (200 ml) was added and kept overnight. On the next day the precipitated solids were filtered off and the filtrate was placed in a current of CO₂ for 3 hr until it is saturated. By this treatment the desired thiohydantoin precipitated out. It was filtrated, dried and crystallised from alcohol. (Yield, 52%, m.p. 222°. (Found S; 14.32. C₂₄H₁₇N₃S₂O requires S; 14.99%).

TABLE 4

Nature of Ar.	Nature of R	Arylidene thiazolidone (VII)				Dibromide (VIII)			
		Yield %	M.P. °C	% sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% bromine	
				Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
Phenyl	Phenyl	—	—	—	—	50	254	30.16	30.54
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	75	220	16.23	16.29	50	170	29.12	28.93
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	208	15.51	15.69	45	164	28.16	28.27
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	165	15.48	15.69	40	195	28.03	28.27
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	70	133	16.33	16.18	50	245	34.56*	35.06
	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	50	255	16.36	16.89	—	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	65	245	16.16	16.29	48	172	28.62	28.93
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	183	14.31	14.61	40	221	26.59	26.76
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	167	14.07	14.61	40	192	26.61	26.76
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	70	225	14.83	14.97	50	203	33.17*	33.28
	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino phenyl	70	235	13.68	13.79	—	—	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	70	207	15.09	15.13	50	120	27.31	27.44
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	Phenyl	65	260	16.67	16.18	45	173	34.96	35.06
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	70	237	14.21	14.97	45	163	33.12	33.28
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	275	14.18	14.46	40	235	32.19	32.44
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	227	14.32	14.46	40	257	32.36	32.44
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	62	227	14.63	14.81	45	154	38.89*	39.02

* Indicate halogen content.

TABLE 5

Nature of Ar.	Nature of R	Benzal thiohyantions (IV)				Dibromo derivatives (V)			
		Yield %	M.P. °C	% Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% Bromine	
				Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.
Phenyl	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	70	155	16.11	16.29	40	>252	28.31	28.93
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	55	238	15.23	15.69	35	>250	28.19	28.27
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	70	249	—	—	35	185	—	—
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	55	220	15.87	16.18	40	180	35.18*	35.06
	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino phenyl	60	>250	15.32	15.76	—	—	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino phenyl	50	247	14.12	14.75	—	—	—	—
	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	75	187	16.56	16.89	—	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	Phenyl	70	>250	16.10	16.18	40	>250	35.29*	35.06
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	75	>250	14.82	14.97	45	>250	33.19*	33.28
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	>259	—	—	35	>250	33.30*	32.44
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	246	14.50	14.64	35	238	32.13*	32.34
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	75	>250	14.63	14.81	40	>250	39.36*	39.02
	<i>p</i> -Dimethylamino phenyl	50	>250	14.46	14.53	—	—	—	—
	<i>p</i> -Diethylamino phenyl	50	218	13.35	13.66	—	—	—	—
	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	60	248	15.16	15.48	—	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	Phenyl	70	239	16.45	16.29	45	231	28.85	28.93
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	75	>260	15.69	15.13	40	>247	29.37	27.42
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	>260	14.18	14.61	30	>260	26.39	26.76
	<i>o</i> -Nitro phenyl	60	>250	14.35	14.61	30	>260	26.51	26.76
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	65	>250	14.86	14.97	35	>250	33.16	33.28
	<i>o</i> -Hydroxy phenyl	60	235	15.19	15.65	—	—	—	—
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	Phenyl	60	>250	13.69	13.49	45	>250	29.32	29.79
	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	65	218	15.16	15.73	40	>250	29.56	28.22
	<i>p</i> -Nitro phenyl	50	>250	15.68	15.17	30	>250	29.36	27.49
	<i>o</i> -Chloro phenyl	65	238	15.32	15.56	45	>250	34.06*	34.21

* Indicate halogen contents.

TABLE 6

Nature of Ar.	Thiohydantoin (IX)				Diazo compound (X)					
	Yield %	M.P. °C	% Sulphur		Yield %	M.P. °C	% Nitrogen		% Sulphur	
			Found	Calcd.			Found	Calcd.	Found	Calcd.
<i>p</i> -Chloro phenyl	50	199	13.36	13.86	60	176	13.16	13.04	14.61	14.89
<i>p</i> -Anisyl	55	221	14.62	14.01	65	156	13.49	13.12	15.17	15.00
<i>p</i> -Tolyl	40	195	14.83	14.51	—	—	—	—	—	—

**3-(4'-Phenyl 5'-sulphonamido phenyl thiazole 2'-yl)
5,5-diphenyl thiohydantoin :**

Sulphanilamide (0.5 g) dissolved in glacial acetic acid (1 ml) and water (25 ml) was diazotised with NaNO_2 (0.25 g in 30 ml of water) in an ice bath. The resulting diazo solution was added gradually with stirring to a previously cooled solution of thiohydantoin (0.45 g) in NaOH (0.5 g in 20 ml of water) kept in an ice bath. After addition the mixture was stirred mechanically for half an hour during which the deep red coloured azodye was separated out. It was crystallised from alcohol. Yield—50%, m.p. 193°. (Found : N, 13.68, S, 16.09; $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{22}\text{N}_6\text{S}_3\text{O}_3$ requires N, 13.77, S, 15.74%).

The properties and analysis of different thiohydantoins and their diazo compounds are given in Table 6.

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